

The mixed-ligand copper(II) complexes in chloroform gave a broad absorption band at 500 nm suggesting their square-planar geometry. The mixed-ligand nickel(II) complexes gave two bands at ~420 nm and 510 nm and in no case absorption bands beyond 600 nm were observed which indicate the square-planar geometry of the complexes.

The negligibly small values ($\Delta M = 5.0 - 7.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) of molar-conductance of the mixed-ligand complexes in chloroform suggest them to be neutral in nature. The I.R. spectra indicate a broad band in the range $3600-3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting that the $-\text{OH}$ groups are unco-ordinated.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for the award of fellowship to one of them (BRS).

References

1. UMA DORASWAMY and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1665
2. B. T. THAKKER and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 615.
3. R. L. DUTTA and ANJANA BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 239.
4. R. W. ASMUSSEN, A. JENSEN and H. SALING, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 1391.
5. E. N. BAKER, D. HALL and T. N. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 680.

Viscosity of NaCl, NaBr and NaNO₃ in Dioxane-Water Mixtures at Different Temperatures

P. P. MISRA, N. C. DAS and P. B. DAS

Department of Chemistry, S.C.S. College, Puri

Manuscript received 4 September 1976, revised 25 March 1977,
accepted 24 November 1977

THE variation of viscosity with temperature and solvent compositions has been employed to study the ion-solvent interaction by many workers¹, both

in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions. In the present communication an attempt has been made to deal with the ion-solvent interaction of NaCl, NaBr and NaNO₃ in dioxane-water mixtures of varying compositions to see the effect of temperature and hydrogen bonding on the B-coefficient of the viscosity equation. The activation energy and the entropy of activation of the viscous flow of these solutions have also been calculated for interpreting the influence of strong electrolytes upon the viscosity of the solvent as a rate process.

All the salts used were of E. Merck 'extra pure varieties'. The samples were recrystallised, dried at 180° and kept in vacuum. Preparation of the solvent, solutions and procedure for measurement were the same as described earlier².

The Jones-Dole equation¹ has been found to be adequate as the plot of $\eta_r - 1/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$ is found to be linear. This is in contrary to that of the results of P. K. Das³ who has used an empirical equation: $\eta_r = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC^x$, where 'x' is an empirical constant without any physical significance. The constant B of the Jones-Dole equation which is regarded as a measure of the ion-solvent interaction could be calculated, from the slope of the above plot, are tabulated in Table 1. The B value increases in case of NaCl and NaNO₃ with increase in temperature whereas it is irregular in case of NaBr. The plot of 'B' vs 't' is linear for NaCl and NaNO₃ whereas it is a curve for NaBr.

Nightingale⁴ has suggested the B value as a measure of ion-dipole interaction. Dioxane is more or less a non-hydrogen bonded solvent. So the ion-dipole interaction energy in the absence of any hydrogen bond energy would be appreciable and the attachment of the solvent molecules to the ions may not be loose and hence no structure formation would occur in the solvents around the ion⁵. The net result will be stronger solvation and more ion-solvent interaction.

Proceeding in the similar manner as that of Nightingale⁵ et al, the energy of activation ΔE , free

TABLE—1

Temp. in °C.	B/l. mol ⁻¹								
	10% D	20% D NaCl	30% D	10% D	20% D NaBr	30% D	10% D	20% D NaNO ₃	30% D
30	0.091	0.1002	0.1554	0.0971	0.1200	0.1510	0.071	0.0955	0.1302
35	0.091	0.1122	0.1662	0.1150	0.1240	0.1700	0.085	0.01085	0.1420
40	0.1400	0.1500	0.2000	0.0661	0.1122	0.1445	0.1020	0.1148	0.1530
45	0.1500	0.1620	0.2200	0.0648	0.1080	0.1120	0.1120	0.1250	0.1600

TABLE—2

Solvent	10% D			20% D			30% D		
	ΔE in K cal	ΔF in K cal	ΔS in E.U.	ΔE in K cal	ΔF in K cal	ΔS in E.U.	ΔE in K cal	ΔF in K cal	ΔS in E.U.
NaCl	4.084	2.290	5.82	4.158	2.491	5.41	4.022	2.530	6.63
NaBr	4.221	2.308	5.97	4.358	2.571	5.70	4.292	2.710	6.79
NaNO ₃	3.852	2.260	5.62	4.048	2.361	5.61	3.894	2.457	6.49
	3.899	2.263	5.70	4.086	2.371	5.23	3.911	2.506	6.51

energy of activation ΔF and entropy of activation ΔS have been computed at 35° and recorded in Table 2. For this calculation our own viscosity data for dioxane-water mixtures have been used. It is observed that the energy and entropy of activation of viscous flow in case of NaCl is greater than that of the solvent whereas it is less in case of NaBr and NaNO₃. The large energy and entropy of activation are attributed to the excess of energy necessary to break the hydrogen bonds in solutions, i.e., for NaCl. In case of bromide and nitrate structure is broken down at all solvent compositions. From Table 2, it is seen that the ion-solvent interaction is of the order Br⁻ > NO₃⁻ > Cl⁻ and is in agreement with that of Kay⁷, who distinguished between the structure breaking and structure making ions by plotting $\Delta(\lambda^0\eta_r)/\Delta T$ vs $\Delta B \frac{1}{2}\Delta T$.

References

1. R. H. STOKES and R. MILLS, 'International Encyclopedia of Physical Chemistry and Chemical Physics'. Vol-3. topic-16, Pergamon Press, N. Y., 1965.
2. P. B. DAS, *J. Instn. of Chem.*, 1976, **48**, 207.
3. P. K. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 613.
4. E. R. NIGHTINGALE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 742.
5. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, 'Electrolyte Solutions', Butterworth Publication, London, 1959, p. 124.
6. E. R. NIGHTINGALE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 1777.
7. R. L. KAY, 'Adv. Chem. Series' (No. 73, edited by R. F. GOULD, American Chemical Society, Washington, D.C., 1968, 1.

Optical Resolution of (±) α-(o, m-carboxyphenylamino)-Arylacetonitriles

S.B. BHATT and A.R. PARIKH

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar

Manuscript received 29 May 1976, revised 19 September

1977, accepted 21 November 1977

α-Aminonitriles being the most important intermediates for the synthesis of amino acids, we have prepared¹⁻⁴ a number of them of type (±) R-C₆H₄-CH(CN)-NH-R', where R = -OH or -OCH₃, R' = o- or m-carboxyphenyl groups. We reported here the optical resolution of α-(o or m-carboxyphenylamino)-m or p-hydroxyphenyl or

p-methoxyphenyl acetonitrile into their enantiomers through their brucine salts. The optical rotations measured in different solvents showed that the introduction of hydroxy group in α-(m-carboxyphenylamino)-phenylacetonitrile decreases the absolute value of optical rotation while that of methoxy group in α-(o-carboxyphenylamino) phenylacetonitrile increases the optical activity.

Experimental

Resolution of (±) α-(o-carboxyphenylamino)-p-methoxyphenylacetonitrile

A clear solution of (±) α-(o-Carboxyphenylamino)-p-methoxyphenylacetonitrile² (5.64 g) and (-)-brucine (7.29 g) in hot acetone (70 ml) on cooling for 72 hrs. deposited a crystalline salt, *crop A* (6.5 g), m.p. 130-32°. On two further crystallisations from a mixture of acetone and chloroform, *crop A* yielded *crop C* (1 g), m. p. 138°. The latter on decomposition yielded the optically pure (+)-nitrile, m.p. 150-51°, [α]_D+70°. Further crystallisations did not increase the optical rotation.

The mother liquor was concentrated to get *crop A'* (6.5 g) m.p. 118-20°, part of which was decomposed to (-)-nitrile [α]_D-23° (C=1.5). On two further crystallisation from a mixture of acetone and chloroform it gave *crop C'* (1 g) m.p. 134° which on decomposition gave (-)-nitrile, m.p. 148° [α]_D-40°. The rotation did not increase on further crystallisation.

Resolution of (±)-α-(m-Carboxyphenylamino)-m-hydroxyphenylacetonitrile :

A clear solution of (±)-α-(m-carboxyphenylamino)-m-hydroxyphenylacetonitrile⁴ (10.72 g) and (-)-brucine (15.58 g) in hot acetone (200 ml.) was subjected to fractional crystallisations as above. The fully active (+)-nitrile, m.p. 155°, [α]_D+20° and (-)-nitrile, m.p. 154-55°, [α]_D-20° were obtained.

Resolution of (±)-α-(m-Carboxyphenylamino)-p-hydroxyphenylacetonitrile :

(-) Brucine (11.8 g) was added to (±)-α-(m-carboxyphenylamino)-p-hydroxyphenylacetonitrile*

TABLE-1

OPTICAL ROTATIONS OF α-AMINONITRILES* OF THE TYPE (+) AND (-) R-C₆H₄-CH(CN)-NH-R' IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS†

Solvent	R=p-methoxy R'=o-carboxyphenyl		R=m-hydroxy R'=m-carboxyphenyl		R=p-hydroxy R'=m-carboxyphenyl							
	(+) isomer	(-) isomer	(+) isomer	(-) isomer	(+) isomer	(-) isomer						
	conc [α] _D	conc [α] _D	conc [α] _D	conc [α] _D	conc [α] _D	conc [α] _D						
Acetone	1.0	+70.0	0.5	-40.0	0.7	+20.0	0.8	-20.0	1.0	+15.0	1.1	-18.0
Ethanol	1.0	+68.0	0.7	-38.0	1.0	+18.0	0.7	-15.0	1.1	+12.0	1.2	-15.0
Methanol	0.7	+60.0	0.8	-35.0	1.2	+15.0	1.0	-12.0	1.2	+10.0	1.0	-15.0
Dioxane	0.6	+58.0	1.0	-38.0	1.1	+12.0	1.1	-12.0	1.2	+10.0	1.3	-12.0
Ethylacetate	0.8	+70.0	1.1	-40.0	1.0	+20.0	1.2	-18.0	1.1	+15.0	1.2	-17.0

* All the isomers gave correct N analysis.

† All the optical rotations were measured at 23°. (l=1)